

A Study on Stroke in Young Adults with Reference to Risk Factors and Hospital Outcome: A Single Centre Prospective Observational StudyDeuri A¹, Kausar N², Das A³, Talukdar P⁴¹Professor, Department of General Medicine, Gauhati Medical College and Hospital²Assistant Professor, Department of General Medicine, Gauhati Medical College and Hospital³Post-graduate trainee, Department of General Medicine, Gauhati Medical College and Hospital⁴Scientist B, Multidisciplinary Research Unit, Gauhati Medical College and Hospital

Received: 25-05-2024 / Revised: 23-06-2024 / Accepted: 26-07-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background and Aim: Even with significant advancements in primary prevention, diagnostic procedures, and treatment, stroke remains one of the principal causes of death. In spite of published findings suggesting that stroke in young is not as common as that in elderly; it should be considered a differential diagnosis in young people with acute neurologic symptoms. The characteristics knowledge gained from research in older patients cannot always be applied to young adults, as the etiology of stroke in this age group differs from that of older patients and influences both diagnostic evaluation and treatment. Following stroke, young adults are incapacitated during their prime years of productivity; therefore, stroke in the young has a disproportionately greater economic impact than stroke in the elderly. Hence this article focuses on the patterns of risk factors, etiology and outcomes in stroke in young adults.

Materials and Methods: We selected 100 patients with stroke in the age group of 15-45 years and followed up these patients from time of admission to time of discharge with thorough history, medical assessment and laboratory and imaging tests. We calculated the NIHSS (National Institute of Health Stroke Scale) score at admission and also modified Rankin score (MRS) of neurological disability at admission and at time of discharge. We tried to evaluate the common risk factors, etiology, hospital outcomes and relation between the NIHSS score at admission to MRS score at discharge.

Results and Discussion: Majority of the study participants were male with a mean age of 38.94 years with an increased prevalence of ischemia stroke. In the haemorrhagic group, male preponderance could be seen however equal incidence was seen in ischemia stroke in both males and females. The most common risk factors in our study population were found to be hypertension, dyslipidaemia, diabetes mellitus and smoking and alcohol consumption was also found to be significant in this young stroke population. Most common etiology however remained undetermined as per TOAST (Trial of ORG 10172 in Acute Stroke Treatment) classification due to constraints in complete evaluation and loss to follow up but a few other determined aetiologies like SLE (Systemic Lupus Erythematosus) vasculitis, Oral contraceptives, Tubercular infective endarteritis, Homocysteinemia, cardioembolic stroke in Rheumatic heart disease (RHD) patients were found to be predominant.

Conclusion: Stroke in young adults is a major public health concern. Prevention is the primary therapeutic strategy for reducing the morbidity and mortality linked to adolescent stroke. Our study's findings suggest that the risk factors for stroke in younger individuals are similar to those previously found in older populations. Young stroke incidence may be considerably reduced by population-based risk factor-focused preventive strategies and interventions.

Keywords: Young Adult, Stroke, TOAST Classification, NIHSS, MRS.

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Introduction

According to current estimates, young individuals (15–45 years old) account for up to 15–18% of all ischemic stroke cases. This incidence of ischemic stroke is on the rise. These young people continue to be at a high risk of having recurrent stroke since they are frequently going through a time in their

lives when important decisions about beginning a family or a job or career need to be made. [1,2] Given that these patients typically still have decades to live, it is crucial to educate them about the causes and risk factors of stroke in order to avoid such dreaded vascular events in future.

[1,3,4] The majority of research suggests that the classic risk factors for stroke—dyslipidaemia, diabetes mellitus, and hypertension—remain the most prevalent risk factors, with hypertension having the highest incidence. Other risk factors that are prevalent in young people include oral contraceptive use, smoking, excessive alcohol consumption, drug use, and migraines. [5,7] Stroke is primarily a disease of middle age and older adults; however, it can sometimes strike people in younger age groups. Young adult strokes appear to be on the rise, which is particularly distressing given the potential for long-term disability and the burden these strokes can place on victims, their families, and the community at large. [6,7,8] There is a dearth of information on stroke among young adults, despite the significant socioeconomic impact that stroke has in this age range. [6,8,9,10] Due to a lack of knowledge and the relative rarity of stroke in comparison to stroke mimics, early detection is still difficult. Furthermore, there are concerns regarding the diagnosis and cause-specific management of stroke in young people due to the varied and relatively infrequent nature of its causes. [11,13,14] Concerns over classic vascular risk factors becoming more common in young people and their possible contribution to an increased risk of stroke, stroke recurrence, and post-stroke death have been brought up by emerging data regarding public health. The aforementioned concerns underscore the significance of devising and implementing tactics aimed at augmenting cognizance and facilitating resource accessibility for juvenile stroke victims, their caregivers, and medical practitioners. [12,13,14,15,16] Good stroke prevention techniques in the young necessitate thorough understanding of risk factors and potential causes. [16] By filling in the knowledge vacuum on stroke in the young, the information gathered from this study will help institutions develop strategies for managing and preventing stroke in this age group. This study, therefore, seeks to determine risk factors and hospital outcome among these patients attending our tertiary health care centre.

Materials and Methods

Study design and setting: Ours is a tertiary care teaching institute in north eastern part of India. This was a single-institute prospective observation study of clinical data collected from patients during December 2023 to June 2024. Data collection was started after obtaining permission from the Institutional Ethics Committee (MC. No.: 190/2007/pt-II/Dec 2023/33). Convenience sampling technique was used. The study followed the guidelines laid down in the Declaration of Helsinki (2008). This manuscript followed the STROBE guideline for reporting.

Sample Size: A total of 100 patients who presented with stroke who fulfilled the inclusion criteria were taken up for the study.

Inclusion Criteria: Any patient in the age group of 15-45 years presenting to the department of medicine with abrupt onset of focal or global neurological deficit attributable to vascular cause and persisting for more than 24 hours was eligible for inclusion in our study. Eligible patients were included after obtaining written informed consent.

Exclusion Criteria:

1. Duration of stroke > 1 week.
2. Patients with history of head injury.
3. Patients with systemic illness malignancy, hemodynamically unstable patients, metabolic emergencies and poor general conditions.

Data collection and analysis: Detailed history and medical assessment of the included patients were carried out at the time of first contact with the treating team. The patients underwent laboratory and imaging study as requested by the treating team. We collected data on age, sex, clinical diagnosis, and laboratory parameters in a prespecified data collection sheet. NIHSS (National Institute of Health Stroke Scale) assessment was done at admission. Modified Rankin Scale (MRS) for Neurologic Disability used to score the condition of the patient between 48 to 72 hours of presentation and at the time of discharge. Statistical analysis has been performed using Prism 8.0. Test used for categorical variables is Fisher's test.

NIHSS Score

The scale contains 11 elements, related to a specific function, which are each evaluated with a score between 0 and 4; some elements only have a scale from 0 to 2. The higher the number, the more impaired that specific function is.

1. **Level of consciousness** -The first element of the scale is level of consciousness, and it contains 3 sub elements (1a, 1b, and 1c). This element evaluates the level of alertness and responsiveness by asking a simple question (the current month and the patient's age), as well as following a simple command (closing and opening the eyes and grasping and releasing a hand).
2. **Best gaze**- This element of the scale evaluates possible damage to a patient's ability to move their eyes normally. It is usually tested by asking the patient to follow an object horizontally.
3. **Visual**- This element tests the patient's visual field, their ability to see things that are not directly in front of them. The focus is on the upper and lower quadrants of the visual field.
4. **Facial palsy**- This element verifies the patient's ability to move facial muscles. The test usually involves asking the patient to show

their teeth or raise their eyebrows while closing their eyes. If the patient is not responsive, the test involves a noxious stimulus (like a bad smell) and observing the facial reaction.

5. **Motor arm-** This element tests the patient's ability to hold their arms up for a certain amount of time. The patient is asked to hold each arm, in turn, at a 90-degree angle if sitting or 45-degree angle if supine, palms down. A score of 0 (the best score) means that the patient can hold their arms up for at least 10 seconds without drift.
6. **Motor leg-** This test is the same as with the motor arm, but with each leg held up at 30 degrees. A score of 0 means that the patient was able to hold the leg up for at least 5 seconds.
7. **Limb ataxia-** The limb ataxia element involves the finger-nose-finger and heel-shin test on both sides. It tests whether there was damage in the cerebellum, which is the motor centre of the brain.
8. **Sensory-** This item tests the sensory abilities of the patient using a pinprick and a noxious (unpleasant) stimulus. The level of response determines the score.
9. **Best language-** To see if the stroke affected the patient's language abilities, they are asked to describe the situation in a picture. Loss of fluency, limitations on ideas that can be expressed, and other elements are used to evaluate the level of aphasia or speech/language impairment.
10. **Dysarthria-** This element tests the level of slurring in a patient's speech.
11. **Extinction and inattention-** This can usually be inferred by all the previous tests. It is related to the level of attention a patient pays to their environment, and their general sensory abilities in each of the five senses.

Severity of grading of NIHSS score: The levels of stroke severity as measured by the NIHSS scoring system are:

- 0 = no stroke
- 1–4 = minor stroke
- 5–15 = moderate stroke
- 15–20 = moderate/severe stroke
- 21–42 = severe stroke

Modified Rankin scale (MRS): The modified Rankin Scale (MRS) is a commonly used scale for measuring the degree of disability or dependence in the daily activities of people who have suffered a stroke or other causes of neurological disability.

It has become the most widely used clinical outcome measure for stroke clinical trials. The scale runs from 0–6, running from perfect health without symptoms to death.

- 0 - No symptoms.

- 1 - No significant disability. Able to carry out all usual activities, despite some symptoms.
- 2 - Slight disability. Able to look after own affairs without assistance, but unable to carry out all previous activities.
- 3 - Moderate disability. Requires some help, but able to walk unassisted.
- 4 - Moderately severe disability. Unable to attend to own bodily needs without assistance, and unable to walk unassisted.
- 5 - Severe disability. Requires constant nursing care and attention, bedridden, incontinent.
- 6 - Dead.

TOAST classification of subtypes of Acute Ischemic stroke: According to the imaging done at the baseline and risk factors associated with the patient, the stroke subtypes are classified accordingly by using classification developed for Trial of Org 10172 in Acute Stroke Treatment (TOAST).

- Large-artery atherosclerosis (embolus/thrombosis)
- Cardio embolism (high-risk/medium-risk)
- Small-vessel occlusion(lacunae)
- Stroke of other determined etiology
- Stroke of undetermined etiology
 - Multiple Aetiologies
 - Incomplete evaluation
 - Complete evaluation

Results and Discussion

A hospital based observational research was conducted on 100 patients who came to Gauhati Medical College and Hospital between December 2023 to June 2024. The study included subjects who were admitted to the medicine ward department of Guwahati Medical College with a diagnosis of stroke and were between the ages of 15 and 45 years.

Majority of the participants in the study were males (55%) as compared to females (45%). Numerous other research conducted on young population showed similar results like in the studies done by S. Sreenivas et al 2020 (Males- 53.3%, females- 46.7%) [17], Nayak SD et al 1997 (males- 76.2%, females- 23.7%) [18] and Shyamal K. Das, et al 2007 [19]. The mean age in our study was 38.94 years which is also similar to the study by Marini C et al 2011[20] where the age range of 35-44 years had the highest incidence of stroke in both males and females.

In other studies, like Chandana, et al. 2017 [21], mean age was found to be 31.9 ± 8.59 years, in Nayak SD et al 1997[18], it was in the range of 40-45 years and also in study done by Hussain, et al 2018 [22] the mean age was 34 years as comparable to our study.

Figure 1: Pie Diagram showing Gender distribution in study population

Figure 2: Column diagram showing age and gender distribution in the study population

In our study population the most frequently recognized risk factors were hypertension (70%), diabetes (23%) and dyslipidaemia (27%) which were also found to be leading risk factors in other studies like Aigner A, et al 2017 [23], Jovanović Z, et al 1996 [24] and Dash D, et al 2014 [25].

Figure 3: Column diagram showing distribution of risk factors in the study population (HTN- hypertension, DM- diabetes mellitus, CAD- coronary artery disease, RHD- rheumatic heart disease, TIA- Transient ischemia attack, F/H/O- family history of)

Hypertension in young adult is considered a primary as well as a secondary cause of death. In addition to increasing stress, hypertension damages the vascular endothelium. This injury primarily affects the large extra cranial arteries, leading to development of thrombus followed by ischemia lesion. In young adults, there is a 28% decrease in the incidence of stroke for every 10–20 mm Hg drop in SBP [26]. Another major risk factor for stroke are the macro-vascular problems brought on by diabetes, which is getting more and more prevalent [27]. Three factors have a major impact on the risk of stroke in young adults: the duration of diabetes, glycosylated haemoglobin (HbA1c), and fasting blood glucose (FBS) levels. Diabetes increases clotting factors and fibrinogen, which increases platelet aggregation and aggravates the growth of arterial thrombus. Young individuals are 11 times more likely to have a stroke than older age groups. [28]

Atherogenic dyslipidaemia increases the risk of stroke and increases the frequency of recurrent strokes in young adults. Higher levels of low-density lipoprotein cholesterol (LDL-C) along with other factors such low high-density lipoprotein cholesterol (HDL-C) ($HDL-C \leq 40$ mg/dL) and high triglycerides ($TGL \geq 150$ mg/dL) are considered to cause atherogenic dyslipidaemia. [29] Apolipoprotein B and A1 levels are also elevated in young stroke patients. Elevated levels of TGL and LDL cause the carotid artery's intimal thickness to rise, hastening the onset of atherosclerosis. It is associated with symptomatic intracranial stenosis identified by cerebral blood vessel magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) or computed tomography (CT) imaging. They have a metabolic pattern that may be impacted by insulin resistance, which eventually causes atherosclerotic vascular disease to advance more quickly [29].

Prior history of stroke/transient ischemic attack (TIA) was seen in (15%) of study population and 10% had a family history of stroke in our study. These results are similar to study done in north India by Dash D, et al 2014 [25] which showed TIA in 26% and family history of stroke in 15.7%

of study population. Also, another study done in Dhaka in 2008 by Miah MN, et al 2012 [30] which yielded similar results.

The study population was evaluated for co-morbidities related to cardiovascular risk factors, such as ischemic heart disease and structural heart diseases. In our study, 12% of participants had RHD, 7% had CAD, 5% had non-valvular AF/Flutter, but no cardiomyopathy. According to Mehndiratta MM et al. 2004 [31], 29.4% of patients with cerebral infarction experienced a cardioembolic stroke. Similar findings were observed in the Dash D. et al. 2014 [25] study on ischemic stroke in young adults; 12.7% of the study group had valvular heart disease, 2.6% had atrial fibrillation, and 5.45% had coronary artery disease. In developing countries, Rheumatic heart disease (RHD) is a significant risk factor for stroke in young adults. RHD accounts for 3-8% of all strokes. It also results in repeated strokes. Early identification and the implementation of prophylactic interventions are necessary to reduce the incidence and recurrence [32].

Also smoking was found to be prevalent in 38% of our study population which is somewhat similar to findings in other studies like Chandana, et al.20 [21], Dr S Sreenivas et al,2020 [17]. The risk of stroke is four times higher in young people who smoke than in non-smokers. The duration and intensity of smoking exposure determine the risk. Significant risk increases if more than 20 cigarettes smoked per day. Smoking accelerates atherogenesis, induce cardiac arrhythmias, arterial thrombosis, and vasospasm [33]. Alcohol use is another modifiable and preventable risk factor for stroke. It's different for males and females. The risk of an ischemic stroke is higher in men who binge drink than in non-drinkers or abstainers from alcohol. Six or more drinks (alcoholic beverages) in a single session are considered binge drinking in men, whereas it is four or more in women. Over indulgence in alcohol has the effects of high blood pressure, which increase the chance of stroke [34] the effects being seen more in females. In our study 32% of the population was addicted to alcohol.

Figure 4: Column diagram showing types of addiction in the study population

Hence in our study, hypertension, diabetes mellitus and dyslipidaemia were found to be the most common risk factors. RHD leading to cardioembolic stroke was another significant risk factor in young adult population.

Also, the behavioural risk factors like alcohol and smoking were found to be prevalent. All these risk factors along with obesity, sedentary life style are modifiable and preventable and thus early detection and proper control will help reduce the disease burden. Of the 100 patients, 52 experienced an infarct, 37 experienced intracerebral haemorrhage,

and 11 experienced subarachnoid haemorrhage. These findings were similar to studies like Hussain, et al 2018 [35] and Vaidya CV, et al 2014 [36] where infarct was the predominant lesion.

In our study, male preponderance was seen in haemorrhage stroke but equal number of male and female were found in the infarct group which is contradictory to other similar studies like Hussain, et al 2018 [35], Vaidya CV et a, 2014 [36] and Balaji Dhanabalan et al 2021 [37] where they found male preponderance in both infarct and haemorrhagic stroke.

Figure 5: Funnel diagram showing the nature of lesion in the study population

Figure 6: Column diagram showing nature of lesion according to gender in the study population

Regarding the site of haemorrhage, majority was found to be capsulo-ganglionic (62%) followed by cortical (19%), thalamic (8%), brain stem bleed (8%) and cerebellar bleed (3%).

Among the ischemia stroke, as per TOAST classification, stroke of undetermined etiology (43.62%) was most predominant in our study which is comparable to other studies like Dash, et al 2014 [25] and Van Alebeek et al 2018 [38]. This may be the result of the fact that majority of patients being unable to afford all of the tests necessary to determine the problem and loss to follow up. However, in the study by Hussain, et al 2018 [35],

large artery atherosclerosis was found to be most prevalent. In our study, 6 patients were found to have other determined etiology of which one had homocysteinemia, one had infective endarteritis (secondary to tuberculosis), two female patients with long term history of oral contraceptive (OCP) intake and two female patients with SLE vasculitis.

Some other prominent causes of stroke in young include cerebral artery dissection found between 10% and 20% of young stroke patients. (In 2001, Schievink WI)[39]. Non-atherosclerotic vasculopathy in the Asian population leading to stroke have been reported to have moyamoya

disease in 6%–15% of cases. (Graggs D. et al., 2011) [40]. Takayasu's arteritis has also been seen

in Indians, and causes 40% of stroke in kids and teenagers (Das SK et al. 2007) [19].

Figure 7: Column diagram showing the site of haemorrhage in the brain in haemorrhagic stroke in the study population

Figure 8: Column diagram showing TOAST classification of ischemia stroke of the study population

Figure 9: Bar diagram showing other determined causes in the TOAST classification in the study population

When the NIHSS scale was utilized in our study to evaluate the severity of stroke, it was discovered that 53% of the patients had moderate stroke. Whereas study like Putaala J. et al 2009 [41] in Helsinki Young Stroke Registry, in contrast, revealed that minor stroke accounted for the largest number at 75.8%, followed by moderate stroke at

13.8%. However, according to a recent study by Matuja et al. published in BMC Neurology 2020 [42], 56.1% of the participants had a severe stroke at the time of admission based on the NIHSS, of which 43.9% were younger than 45 years old. In this study, mild stroke (35.8%) was the second most prevalent group.

Figure 10: Pie diagram showing NIHSS classification

At the time of admission and at the end of the hospital stay, the modified Rankin scale was used to evaluate the stroke outcome. Most study participants had severe disabilities (Stage 5) at admission, whereas most had moderately severe disabilities (Stage 4) at the end of their hospital stay.

Figure 11: Column Diagram showing MRS score at the time of admission in the study population

Figure 12: Bar Diagram showing MRS score at the end of hospital stay in the study Population

There was a positive and significant correlation between NIHSS on admission and MRS at discharge, with a P value of 0.0068, that is, mild to moderate NIHSS score had a moderate MRS score at discharge while with a moderate-severe to severe NIHSS score had a severe disability (MRS severe) at discharge. Hence to some extent NIHSS score can predict the outcome in terms of MRS. With a lower NIHSS score, the outcome is favourable whereas with a higher NIHSS score prognosis is poor.

Conclusion

Young adult stroke is a serious public health issue. The main therapeutic approach for lowering the morbidity and death associated with juvenile stroke is prevention. The results of our study indicate that the risk factors for stroke in younger persons are comparable to those that have been previously identified in older groups. Preventive approaches and interventions aimed at certain population-based risk factors may significantly lower the incidence of stroke in young people. Based on the TOAST classification, the most common subtype of stroke in the current study was undetermined etiology considering the incomplete evaluation owing to financial constraints and loss to follow up. However, the other determined aetiologies like tubercular infective endarteritis, autoimmune disease like SLE vasculitis, Homocysteinemia, Takayasu's arteritis, RHD leading to cardioembolic stroke and non-valvular Atrial Fibrillation and other such causes are to be sought for and suspected based on history and clinical examination while dealing with a stroke in young individual. Finding the appropriate aetiologies and improving the prognosis of stroke in young adults will be greatly impacted by doing a thorough etiological

investigation and managing the condition accordingly. Although categorization models are not completely accurate, scoring methods with high prediction accuracy can be useful in determining the severity and prognosis of strokes as well as in analysing the course of the condition. However, this study has some limitations, including a limited sample size, a quick turnaround time, and potentially non-generalizable outcomes. Therefore, it is challenging to get a firm conclusion. Large prospective epidemiological and analytical research is therefore necessary to get a definitive conclusion.

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